

NEWS

John G. Wolbach Library

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The [John G. Wolbach Library](#) combines the collections of the [Harvard College Observatory](#) (HCO) Library and the [Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory](#) (SAO) Library, forming one of the world's preeminent astronomical collections. The joint collection is known as the John G. Wolbach Library at the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics.

The principal subject areas contained within the Wolbach Library collection include astrophysics and related topics in physics, chemistry, applied mathematics, geophysics, and engineering. The Wolbach Library serves the research and technical support staff of the CfA, scientists and students of the Astronomy and other departments of Harvard University, scientists from many universities and colleges in the Boston area and around the world.

The Wolbach Library provides access to information in a variety of forms to CfA staff by building, organizing, managing, housing, and preserving collections; by offering reference services and consultation; by providing services in online literature searches, and interlibrary loan requests; by employing all appropriate technologies for finding and disseminating information; and by contributing to and drawing from remote databases, including the [SAO/NASA Astrophysics Data System](#) (ADS). The Wolbach Library participates in local, national, and international networks and cooperative activities which promote the sharing of information, access to recorded knowledge, and the support and advancement of scholarly communication.

- [John G. Wolbach Library](#)
- [Obituary of John Gray Wolbach, 1917-2000](#)

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1955

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1956

[SAO moves to HCO](#)

[John G. Wolbach Fund](#)

1959

[SAO Library formed](#)

1969

[Joyce Watson, SAO Librarian](#)

1971

[Library named](#)

1973

[CFA formed](#)

1974

[Joyce Watson, CfA Librarian](#)

1975

[HCO & SAO merge](#)

1985

[Committee formed](#)

1987

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1990

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1992

[Collections merge](#)

1994

[Recommendations feedback](#)

2009

[Head Librarian retires](#)

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2010

[New Head Librarian](#)

2013

[Unified Astronomy Thesaurus \(UAT\)](#)

2015

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